

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF MOBILE APPLICATIONS IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the advantages and disadvantages of mobile applications in the educational system, as well as the technology of e-learning management.

Key words: Educational system, mobile applications, computer, tablet, phone, smartphone, gadget, device, information technology.

РОЛЬ И ЗНАЧЕНИЕ МОБИЛЬНЫХ ПРИЛОЖЕНИЙ В СИСТЕМЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье анализируются преимущества и недостатки мобильных приложений в системе образования, а также технологии управления электронным обучением.

Ключевые слова: Образовательная система, мобильные приложения, компьютер, планшет, телефон, смартфон, гаджет, устройство, информационные технологии.

Nowadays, the exchange of information is an integral part of the life of every person. Devices such as phones, tablets, computers, smartphones become the basis of digital life. With technological progress, electronic devices are gaining new and new opportunities that allow them to perform increasingly complex tasks, as well as process more data flow.

The results of many studies show that in most cases, young students are familiar only with the gaming side of computer life. At the same time, there is not enough data

on the use of mobile applications, tablets, smartphones and other smart devices for general education schools to receive additional knowledge.

Learning subjects from public schools through mobile applications is a relatively new way and is just gaining popularity.

Currently, there is no strong enough basis for creating a new training system based on applications, but the head of our country Sh. M. In the decree PF-158 on the strategy “Uzbekistan -2030” dated September 11, 2023 by Mirziyoyev, he emphasizes the main points related to the creation of an educational system that fully meets international standards, bringing the general secondary education system to a new level, creating new textbooks, exercise books, methodical manuals and mobile applications for educators with about 700 titles, as well as creating 1000 multimedia programs for tablets based on new generation textbooks [1].

In connection with the above, it makes sense to use the mobile application as an auxiliary element in the educational system.

In terms of the organization of educational activities and their use in the creation of exercises, mobile applications can be divided into two main groups: practical mobile applications, that is, those that were originally not intended for educational purposes and educational mobile applications. Educational mobile applications, in turn, are known as training programs and Shell applications (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Mobile applications in education

It can be assumed that similar programs will be created in the future, taking into account the educational goals of the relevant educational levels, within the framework of the development and formation of a unified concept of informatization of Education. Examples of this are:

– education management systems (e.g. MOODLE, Edmodo, Schoology, etc.) have a mobile version;

- blogs (e.g. blogger.com, has a convenient mobile phone (which works on both Windows and iOS, Android);

Instagram Facebook, instagram, among other popular social networks, began to be used more often to create language courses in the form of multimedia projects, etc.;

- educational programs-shells with ready-made templates for creating tests and assignments to improve the communicative skills of students (for example, talim.uz, smartland.uzedu.uz, maktab.uz, eduportal.uz, kitob.uz, learningApps.org, educaplay.com. studystack.com. umaigra.com. classtools.ru, classtools.net, onlinetestpad.com, quiziz.com, kahoot.com and other.).

Below are the three most popular OSS cited:

1st Place-Android system (78%) - this is the operating system from Google. It is distributed free of charge, the technical parameters requirements for the mobile device are minimal. These features made it the most popular among the largest smartphone manufacturers.

2nd place-Apple iOS (15.2%) - this is the operating system mutlaaqa is closed, since it is necessary to pay for each product. This platform is distinguished by high quality and stability of its work – this is undoubtedly its dominant side. In addition to it, it is easy to use. Another dominant aspect is security. At the Apple Store, all applications are carefully checked. The disadvantage of this system is that it is only available on Apple devices.

3rd place-Windows Phone (2.5%) - this system was produced by Microsoft. It is not as popular as the above systems, but most users believe that WP leaders can compete with companies. In this, the interface is very convenient and unusual: instead of widgets, “living (tiles) tiles” (live tiles). They display information on the screen without opening applications (for example, calendar, weather and hkz.). Based on the advantages is the speed and trouble-free operation of the interface [2].

Students themselves increasingly prefer mobile technologies and use them regularly in their personal lives. Therefore, it is not surprising that for modern young people it is not so difficult to apply mobile devices not only for their own specific needs, but also for learning. For a long time, a tendency has arisen for students to independently use mobile devices during extracurricular independent study, namely:

Communication – exchange of information with each other;

Camera – photo of text, etc.;

Sound recorder – recordings of the voice of the teacher reading the lecture;

Mobile browser-access to sites;

Audio player for listening to voice accompaniment lectures;
Conducting experiments;
Tools for translating foreign sources.

One of the advantages of using mobile technology in the learning process is that students will be able to control the information received. Also, the freedom to choose for itself from the vast amount of information available will open the reader to endless learning opportunities, which will give him freedom and independence. Unlike the traditional form of teaching materials and assignment, mobile education uses innovative technologies, with the help of which changes occur in the process of training. Modern services such as social networks, cloud storage, media hosting are used to deliver a certain type of data and have hosted useful information there.

In summary, "mobile education" is the solution to a number of educational problems that students face by using portable devices such as phones, smartphones, tablets, computers, sometimes laptops, etc. This type of Education works in modern times, providing up-to-date information materials.

It should also be noted that the relationship between the student and the teacher still plays a large role in the learning process, since it is emphasized that students mainly use their own techniques for computer and mobile applications only for entertainment. But since mobile applications are included in the educational system, there will also be changes in perception, since it will not be something fundamentally new, and readers will not perceive the tasks on the gadget screen only as a toy of another color.

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